

Python in Heliophysics Community Spring 2023 Meeting

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13743019>

Meeting materials are located at <http://heliopython.org/meetings/>

Table of Contents

Python in Heliophysics Community Spring 2023 Meeting	1
Table of Contents	2
Participants	3
Meeting Overview	4
Core Packages Updates (and thoughts from authors)	5
HAPI	5
PlasmaPy	6
SunPy	7
SpacePy	7
Pysat	7
Kamodo	8
PySPEDAS	8
Other packages and efforts	8
Valuable Collaborations	9
Open Science Session (end of Day 1)	10
Unconference Notes	12
Running on the Cloud/Cloud Enabling	12
Maintainer Burnout	16
Proposal Development	17
Hackathon Results	18
PyHC Virtual Environment	18
Improving Sideways Interoperability	18
General Meeting Notes	19
Improving PyHC (meetings and overall)	20
Next Steps	22
References	23
Final agenda	24

Participants

76 people registered to participate in the hybrid Spring 2023 meeting via the meeting's Google sign up form. Of those 76 people, approximately 10-15 participants attended in-person, with the rest participating via the Zoom. Meeting participants' home institutions (as indicated by responses to the Google sign up form) included the following:

- NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
- Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian
- LASP
- Southwest Research Institute
- University of New Hampshire
- NMSU
- National Institute for Space Research, Brazil
- University of Oulu, Finland
- University of Turku
- CU Boulder CIRES/NOAA SWPC
- CU Boulder
- SSL - UC Berkeley
- University of Alabama in Huntsville
- Johns Hopkins University Applied Physics Laboratory
- Predictive Science
- United States Naval Academy
- High Altitude Observatory
- ESAC
- Community Coordinated Modeling Center, NASA Goddard Space Flight Center
- Common Action/CfHA
- National Institute for Space Research (INPE), Brazil
- NASA JPL
- National & Kapodistrian University of Athens
- Universidad de Santiago de Chile
- Polyneme LLC
- University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)
- Stoneris
- GSFC 672 / ADNET Systems
- George Mason University
- University of Delaware
- Wright State University
- School of Space Research, KyungHee University, South Korea

- National Solar Observatory
- NASA Scientific Visualization Studio

Meeting Overview

The Spring 2023 meeting was spread over a three-day period, where each day ran approximately from 9 AM to 5 PM (slight fluctuations to accommodate delays in start time). The meeting took place in Boulder, CO at LASP's LSTB building. As with prior meetings, the meeting organizing committee chose to use the Zoom platform for the hybrid component, as Zoom is familiar to PyHC members (it is already in use for the bi-weekly PyHC telecons), it consistently provides good quality video and sound, and it lends itself nicely to large group video calls and breakout rooms. All sessions except for the Unconferences and Hackathons were recorded and uploaded to the PyHC's YouTube¹ ([see link here](#)), with videos uploaded to [the meeting web page](#) at the end of the meeting². All presentation slides were collected and put into the [Presentations folder](#) on the meeting's Google Drive³.

The meeting began Tuesday, May 16th, and ran through Thursday, May 18th. Content of each day was as follows:

- Day 1: Core project updates, other PyHC project updates, with discussions on Geomagnetic Field Models within Heliophysics, as well as the PyHC Executable Paper: the science version.
- Day 2: Tutorials (geomagnetic datacubes, HelioCloud (the basics and recent updates), package Submission to PyHC, and a clean code refresher), followed by unconference sessions on 1) running on the cloud/cloud enabling, maintainer burnout, and proposal development.
- Day 3: presentation on "Heliophysics ScienceCore curriculum development with emphasis on knowledge representation techniques to increase usability of NASA cloud-based datasets" - An overview and where PyHC fits in, as well as presentations/discussions surrounding a pyOpenSci intro, ChatGPT and PyHC, PyHC's TESS '24 solar eclipse event, and wrap up. An optional hackathon session took place after the meeting adjourned officially, in the afternoon.

1

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6ZIH0yEyu08&list=PLDKhoNyHGTFZc8kaT93yNXqC_Xiq-FIFP&pp=iAQB

2 <https://heliopython.org/meetings/spring2023/>

3

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1z4gLO4gmvVTLHhHsG-HcHew8tb3rzklZ?usp=drive_link

Core Packages Updates (and thoughts from authors)

HAPI

HAPI v3.2 will better accommodate more descriptive metadata and easier access to those metadata, including coordinate system information. Another new feature coming in version 3.2 is to support serving links as one way to serve images, but this is not recommended in general. The stated preference is for HAPI servers to serve data in a standard format, not links to data files. However, the SIAP (Simple Image Access Protocol) IVOA standard allows for this and is shown to be an effective approach (Dowler et al. 2016). HAPI would like to expand to serve coordinate transformation matrices and offer file format conversions, better visualizations and possibly search capabilities through various interfaces built on top of HAPI servers. Additionally, the related data adapters project needs about 20% more funding to be completed. Jon V. also noted a potential to include data cleaning as a separate service on top of HAPI servers.

Some thoughts: HAPI's primary purpose is to serve data in standard formats to the community through a standard API. Serving data carries with it a community expectation of quick-look visualizations, not necessarily high quality or complex visualizations as in many analysis workflows, but at least enough for a cursory look. The current visualization methods in HAPI are sufficient for this. Some improvements could be an update to a more interactive visualization approach, such as that already built on top of HAPI elsewhere by Eelco Doornbus and the new iSWA HAPI cygnet, possibly even by collaborating with such a project. That being said, higher quality and more complex visualizations belong in the analysis packages for each data type, such as pySPEDAS, Kamodo and others. In those cases, HAPI and similar services should serve as the 'plumbing' to get data into those more complex visualization routines. Feedback from a HAPI package lead confirms the two-pronged approach described here - improvement in the basic visualization in HAPI and serving as plumbing to more complex visualizations - is the approach desired.

Offering coordinate transformation matrices through HAPI is one reasonable way to offer a complex capability through a website, an API, and into multiple PyHC packages. If coordinate transformations for both scalars and vectors are offered through both a website interface and a HAPI server, as HAPI does for data, then that approach could circumvent the current requirement of installing multiple packages to convert from one coordinate system to another and utilize cloud systems to speed up the necessary calculations (especially for vector conversions). For example, at least three packages are currently required to convert a satellite trajectory from the 'teme' coordinate system available through AstroPy (package 1) to the SM

coordinate system available in SpacePy (package 2) as an access point to a model-specific coordinate system available in Kamodo (package 3) before interpolating through modeled data. This is not only a lot to expect of a science user, but is a significant barrier due to the combined installation difficulties of those packages. Additionally, no vector conversion capabilities are offered in PyHC, except possibly for conversions contained in AstroPy or SpiceyPy. Offering coordinate transformations as a service on top of HAPI appears to be a good way forward to lowering the complex software interdependency barrier.

The Space-Time Coordinate Transform (STCT) working group is a grassroots effort starting up to define what those coordinate transformation matrices should be and what the software needs to be to perform those transformations, which is led by Robert Weigel with participation from several others in the community. The matrix definitions determined by that group are expected to be made available through multiple methods, including an API (possibly HAPI), incorporated into a coordinate conversion software package aligning with the PyHC standards, and served through a website interface. The discussion on the software design of the package is also a main goal of a session on Interoperability in Python at DASH in October of 2023 in Maryland ⁴.

Infrastructure resources would also benefit from collaborating with HAPI. For example, a deeper collaboration between SPDF and HAPI would increase the number of datasets available through HAPI, thus making more datasets easily accessible; could avoid the work and added interface complexity of developing custom APIs, and would streamline user access to the data through various analysis packages, especially since many PyHC packages use HAPI to ingest data to some extent. This ties into possible components of PyHC's long-term vision briefly discussed in the last section of this document.

An interesting item to note here is that since many PyHC packages already use HAPI to ingest data, HAPI could be used as an interface between packages for interoperability (e.g. pulling data from SpacePy into Kamodo and back), but that capability would require automatic launching of dynamic HAPI servers, which have not been developed yet. Additionally, SunPy does not (currently) use HAPI to ingest data, but instead uses fido, so interoperability with SunPy will need to be performed through fido.

PlasmaPy

The leader of the PlasmaPy package, Nick Murphy, has become a recognized resource in the community to teach good coding practices in a congenial manner. He would be a great person to fund to lead general classes for the community, such as 'How to use GitHub for beginners',

⁴ <http://dash.heliophysics.net/sessions.html#6>

general python programming, and software development resources for the community. These efforts would be great to build an entry path into software development in Heliophysics, and it should be coordinated with currently-existing summer schools on the topic. PlasmaPy is currently funded by NSF and will pursue funding from DOE.

SunPy

SunPy has multiple affiliated packages, a vibrant community, and mature software. However, it needs funding to continue advancing its capabilities (e.g. better support for multi-dimensional data and documentation refactoring), even to advance beyond Python into an analysis environment approach (e.g. a website/GUI interface).

One important question that was discussed is how to preserve SolarSoft's capabilities outside of IDL, likely into a SunPy affiliated package. One such package has a beginning on the task (XRTPy), but the effort is much larger than can be done in someone's spare time and needs funding. AI tools could aid in converting from IDL into Python, but developers are needed to finish the conversion and test for accurate performance. Such work is included in the NASA ROSES HTM announcement of opportunity⁵ and in some NSF opportunities.

SpacePy

This package can be tricky to install, especially on Windows machines. This difficulty arises from the FORTRAN and C routines it includes for coordinate conversions and field-line tracing for BATS-R-US data. The authors here note that SpacePy would greatly benefit from funding to address installation issues and updating their documentation. pyOpenSci (later) will be a great resource in the installation puzzle. Using SpacePy as a 'test package' in the collaboration between pyOpenSci and PyHC would be a great learning example on how that interface can work, and a test of how their current approaches to the issue work for a PyHC package.

Pysat

Advancements in the pysat package are generally driven by user contribution in the ITM domain and generally include cleaning routines for ITM observational data. However, some new capabilities were demonstrated, including bin-averaging and a way to graphically represent when observed and modeled data are both available.

5

<https://nspires.nasaprs.com/external/solicitations/summary.do?solId={17553B8F-C32A-1AD2-2A61-78670D6D21F4}&path=&method=init>

Kamodo

This package is a NASA open source software package. One thought for improving Kamodo (and future PyHC packages) - it has a NOSA v1.3 software license, which was mentioned as a barrier instead of a positive property. The NASEM study on open source software also refers to this license as a ‘barrier to community contribution’ (p. 25 of NASEM 2018). The findings and conclusions presented in the NASEM study may warrant excluding NOSA v1.3 as an acceptable open source license in PyHC’s standards. If being a NASA open source software package is so restricting, as the NASEM study shows, then that needs to be communicated with NASA HQ.

PySPEDAS

PySPEDAS is the growing python version of SPEDAS, an IDL code. This package is pushing towards GUI interfaces for visualizations, with the capability to download a script for others to reproduce the same result. Another example of such an interface is from Kamodo-core, the package upon which the Kamodo-ccmc PyHC package is built upon (e.g. Fig. 7 of Ringuette et al. 2022) and SPRINTS (Fig. 5 of the same paper). However, these examples do not offer the option to download a script for others to reproduce the same results. Giving funding to PySPEDAS to push this boundary would be a great way to push the other PyHC packages towards that goal. This package’s contributors (e.g. Jim Lewis) would be a great resource for converting SolarSoft into Python or some other free language.

Other packages and efforts

- Geo coordinate conversion tools are available in ApexPy, AACGMV2, and OCBpy specifically for high latitudes (presented by Angeline Burrell). Those packages should ideally be part of the coordinate conversion conversation at DASH and the working group led by Robert (Bob) Weigel.
- CCSDSpy (Daniel de Silva) has been used by several missions to process binary spacecraft data in the CCSDS data format. The package is currently supported by mission institutions (e.g. JPL).
- Alec Engell presented on streamlining data analysis on the cloud, but the file format is Zarr, which requires a file conversion step. Packages used included Bokeh, fsspec and kerchunk. Later discussion on software operation on cloud data pointed to fsspec as a possible common-ground for PyHC packages to work seamlessly with data on the cloud stored in s3 buckets and similar methods.
- XRTpy (presented by Joy Velasquez): Working on converting part of SolarSoft into Python. This and other similar efforts to convert pieces of SolarSoft into Python need to

be pushed forward, mentored and accelerated by community involvement and funding to preserve those capabilities.

- HelioCloud (presented by Alex Antunes) is a maturing platform for the PyHC community to test software capabilities on the cloud and for science analyses.
- Discussion started on a standard for hosting geomagnetic field models (e.g. Tsyganenko, IGRF, etc) in Python packages in PyHC. Discussion concluded that the interface to all of these models should be the same and return the same thing - the magnetic field (e.g. same component order?). Could imitate (or build into) the VIRES magnetic field visualization (see information on tool where users can switch between magnetic field models via a drop-down list. Want the pieces underneath such a surface to be standardized in ways that ensure efficiency and speed. **We need to ensure this conversation continues, possibly in PyHC telecons or dedicated sessions at later PyHC meetings or related conferences (e.g. GEM, TESS, AGU).**

Valuable Collaborations

- Donny Winston presented his funded TOPST work to build Heliophysics Open Science resources. PyHC can be a great resource for this by contributing pieces of tutorials to example workflows and analyses. Since this work can be done via honorarium, collaborating with the TOPST effort can also easily plug into the current need to develop PyHC multi-package tutorials for the PyHC Gallery (two results with one effort).
- Leah Wasser presented on the pyOpenSci group, which offers a free peer-review service for open science software (not just open-source). Conversations on previous PyHC telecons agreed that PyHC packages should be officially reviewed for both their alignment with good software practices and with the PyHC standards, but no one volunteered to do this since the work is extensive. Collaborating with pyOpenSci looks like an ideal way to tackle this problem. Membership in PyHC could require all members to assist pyOpenSci in the review of at least one other package, and PyHC leadership could assess each submitted package based solely on its alignment with the PyHC standards (on top on the standard review provided by pyOpenSci). A big plus here is that the packages can then be easily approved in JOSS (the Journal of Open Source Software) AND get pyOpenSci and PyHC badges on their repositories. This process could easily be required and funded by HTM proposals. Another plus is that the pyOpenSci review process checks for redundancy of capability among packages, which is expected to increase collaboration between packages in the community and across domains.

Open Science Session (end of Day 1)

- Rebecca Ringuette and Gretchen Gueguen (OSF) paired up to lead a session on open science, the PyHC executable paper, and PyHC's role in the push towards open science. The session spent about half the time outlining the three topics and half the time on discussing them. The discussion was lively at times, attesting to the community's willing involvement in such activities. Four main questions were considered in the discussion, hosted on a miro board⁶, and are repeated here:
 - (1) What PyHC software changes are needed to better support the open science experiment? Which of these need funding?
 - (2) How can PyHC better advertise data access and analysis support in PyHC packages?
 - (3) How can PyHC help with accessibility issues for modeled data?
 - (4) How can PyHC prepare for, collaborate with, and enable the next generation of infrastructures?
- Some common threads in the answers to these questions include:
 - Community desire to have easy ways to install and run PyHC packages (pip install, containerized, etc), avoid package dependency conflicts, and have a referenceable (e.g. with a DOI) environment with a release schedule (yearly) coordinated with other community package releases available in multiple ways (pip install PyHC, conda-forge, and containers). Progress on this was made in a hackathon on the last day of the meeting.
 - Recognition that PyHC packages need to run seamlessly on data downloaded to the users machine, data hosted on the cloud, and data retrieved through HAPI/fido. This was discussed further in an unconference session on the second day. Also need to easily/automatically adapt to a broad range of hardware infrastructures (e.g. GPUs and systems with a large number of cores/processors).
 - The lack of discoverability and community knowledge of PyHC packages. Some suggested ways to address this include DOIs for all packages (and requiring them to be cited in publications and websites), improved search capability on the PyHC website (possibly by adding SPASE metadata records) and links from the archives to notebooks related to a given dataset.
 - In a related collection of comments, funding for an army of tutors was requested. This army of tutors would use a (yet to be generated) set of standard single and multi-package tutorials to give tutorials for community at the PyHC summer school, tutorial sessions and booths at various conferences, virtual office hours,

⁶ <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMKYw40w=/>

and other outreach opportunities (e.g. classes hosted at institutions/agencies). These tutorials could be sourced from the growing PyHC gallery, PyHC summer school materials, and package documentation. Honoraria should be given for original (and useful) contributions outside of pre-existing materials.

- Other requests could be handled by a partnership with PyOpenSci, such as guidance on how to include scripts in other languages in a package build, metrics on package usefulness, and improvements on documentation.
- The remaining requests can be viewed at the link to the miro board above. Screenshots of the contributed comments are included in the two figures below.

Figure 1: Contributed comments for Questions 1 (left) and 2 (right).

Figure 2: Contributed comments for Questions 3 (left) and 4 (right).

Unconference Notes

The group (both in-person and virtual) made good progress in planning the next steps for running on data in the cloud by choosing fsspec as a possible way forward, and some great conversations occurred for burnout. The burnout conversation naturally progressed to a proposed solution: adding backup people to proposals and/or smooth out funding across smaller institutions, possibly via multi-institutional alliances. These sessions were not recorded to keep with the spirit of unconferences. Summary notes were taken below, with personal details and identifying information removed.

Running on the Cloud/Cloud Enabling

Main topic ideas

- PyHC projects operating in the cloud (data not on local filesystem w/o writing access in everything)
- Run PyHC packages on data in S3
 - Files are a “GET” request; will occasionally fail to download due to only 99.9% availability
 - Object store, not a file system

- Users should be aware of where files are, but not have to worry about implementing it
 - easy to learn, hard to master (should be the goal)
- How much does fsspec solve? It abstracts local, S3, ftp, etc. Does it work with astropy/FITS, xarray, HDF5, CDF, netCDF3?
 - netCDF3 not supported by HDF5 so experiments needed
- Can packages that currently accept file names also be made to accept file-like objects or fsspec file handles?
 - We'd want to vet the API to make sure it's something we can live with (even if it stops being supported?)
- Getting a handle on cloud costing is key
- EBS is different from EFS (EFS = no cost if empty, EBS = constant cost) and the instance store is fast but potentially costly (?)
- Talk to Earth Science, OpenDAP people who solved this 5 years ago, find their lessons learned (via James Gallagher and Nathan Potter⁷)
- EC2 pricing table showing different types of storage for different instances types⁸.
- Cdflib (pure python): already supports s3 or http paths; netcdf4 does not, but there is a package S3netCDF4 which supports this. But maybe additional support for specifying inputs via fsspec would be a good idea.

Whiteboard:

⁷ <https://www.opendap.org/about/engineering>

⁸ <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/pricing/on-demand/>

autodownload - maybe not in pkg?

h5netcdf & Xarray use S3

S3 objects can read a subset

fsspec → unified pythonic interface (S3FS)
to local & cloud (dask, pandas...)

Rebecca, Sandy
Jon M

S3 get can soft fail (not 100% availability)
fsspec will raise exception

s3netcdf	h5netcdf
lotsa setup	no setup

AWARE of it but not need to implement

reader_utilities.py line 24 → Kamodo

should PyHC
accept
file-like
object

(eg. from
fsspec)

(S3FS)

Py HC projects operate in cloud
(data not on local filesystem
w/o writing access in
everything)

Run Py HC packages on data in S3

S3fs + boto3 hunt

(latest boto3 doesn't work)

does AWS have local temp storage?

may depend on instance type
(most expensive)

Marcin

→ provision EBS pay whether full or empty
(can be attached to instances)

EFS - pay by what's stored
(mountable to EC2)

Instance storage depends on type of instance

(can even have local nvme SSD)

directly tied to instance → not persistent
across reboot

pay by second of uptime

paying EBS fees to store image

doesn't even exist on all instances

tempfile open is probably
in here

Jon V - Earth Science / opendap
lessons learned

Best practices
for temp/scratch?

(future telecon
topic)

Actions moving forward:

- Rebecca & Sandy: look into fsspec and how it might help with FITS, CDF, NetCDF3, NetCDF4/HDF
- Marcin: write up his AWS optimization/cheats for effective caching on real problems and storage strategies in general. (play with HelioCloud, maybe the instance storage is there already, then we could experiment locally)
- Jon V.: reach out to James Gallagher etc on cloud transition, particularly how they handled temporary scratch

Maintainer Burnout

- Define burnout and the types of burnout
 - NASA talk on this recently⁹
 - Beginning stage: need a break and then fine
 - Late stage: don't care anymore and a break doesn't help
- Actionable ways to reverse burnout:
 - 15 min occasional presentations on burnout at PyHC telecons and meetings?
 - These kinds of meetings can be helpful to energize (especially live meetings), especially after the Pandemic years
 - Call outs to people for work done at meetings?
 - Identify mechanisms to allow for all members to have input, not simply just the ones who naturally speak up first.
 - Be conscientious of ensuring requested work has funding behind it where at all possible. Avoid overloading people with unfunded requests.
 - Connect to things you value in general, work on things you enjoy, and feel you're making a difference
 - What validates us at work? Not being funded makes work feel invalidated. Mental health oftentimes correlates to funding situations.
 - Workplace idea: Volunteer Amnesty Day, where people can say "I won't be continuing doing this"
- What about leadership / personal management / management courses at the front end of PyHC meetings?
 - Perhaps start something the day *prior* to the meeting starting officially.
 - Or, structure the meeting so that there are enough breaks for people to go for walks, have longer talks, etc.
- Psychological safety
 - Ask questions without shame for it. Bring true / authentic self into the room.

⁹ <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Ntxjjk09jhhd1mDgOL-jKsAFpNbiED27/view?usp=sharing>

- Marginalized groups deal with extra overhead in terms of how they present themselves, etc. that can increase burnout risk. This needs to be addressed in handling future matters.
- Affirmations help!
- Addressing the academia funnel
 - Academia has a tendency to put everyone into the same pipe, with a lack of release valves.
 - Lack of job security if you don't get funded... what to do then?
 - Enter... "The Heliophysics Proposal and Soft Money Guild"
 - share proposal ideas/opportunities/leftover funds if you don't have the time, but think another would be a great fit?
 - Ideas relevant to NASA TOPS? Should we contact them?
 - Ability to float proposal stuff depends on whether you're correctly plugged into professional networks (e.g. the [US-RSE](#)).
 - Sticking point: some institutions don't let the money float out once it's in. How to address this?
 - Float the rich years into the lean years.

Proposal Development

- Proposal Development
 - Ask to be on reviewer panels
 - NSPIRES
 - Ask Reinhard Friedel about upcoming opportunities.
 - NSF
- Funding
 - Models for funding in the future (e.g. PyHC leadership activities).
 - Data and computing working group is needed in heliophysics to guide decisions.
 - Focus on publication efforts; a metric that is valued by headquarters. RSEs should be more on par with scientists, which requires publishing software in open source journals. "Our community helps build the tools AND we generate more papers!"
- Some proposal opportunities^{10, 11}

¹⁰

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1IYhvN3s2zJySdSCjSlgf_DOSauA8W7jRVhZ9oupozPE/edit#gid=0

¹¹

<https://www.simonsfoundation.org/grant/scientific-software-research-faculty-award/?tab=how-to-apply>

Hackathon Results

PyHC Virtual Environment

On the last day of the PyHC Spring 2023 meeting, Shawn led a hackathon centered around trying to create one Python virtual environment that has every PyHC package installed. Previous work on this resulted in the PyHC 2022 summer school container¹², but was limited in the number of packages included. Roughly ten people participated in total, with three of them participating remotely. At the start of the hackathon, Shawn presented a spreadsheet he had previously generated which showed allowable version ranges of the 250+ packages that the ~60 PyHC packages depend on. The group condensed the requirements into one "requirements.txt" file that could be pip installed. The file was then uploaded to a new GitHub repository¹³ and the group coordinated their development around that repo for the rest of the hackathon. A second requirements file was made to automate the (attempted) installation of the latest versions of all the PyHC packages. To the group's pleasant surprise, the pip installations worked on the first try, proving that the generated version ranges in Shawn's initial spreadsheet were valid. An "import-test.py" file was added to the repo which runs import statements for every PyHC package before printing a success message. This script did not succeed on anyone's machine on the first try, for various reasons, so the rest of the hackathon centered around fixing environment issues to get the script to succeed on as many different machines as time allowed. Windows machines proved problematic, but by the end of the hackathon, Shawn and a couple others were able to successfully run "import-test.py" on their Macs.

Additionally, the in-person members of the Kamodo and SpacePy packages collaborated on improving their installation methods across operating systems (including Windows). We consider this hackathon a success because of that. We successfully created a Python virtual environment that was capable of importing every single PyHC package for the first time ever. This was a milestone moment for PyHC. Future work will involve making this environment as portable as possible so that anyone can use it.

Improving Sideways Interoperability

One hackathon session focused on improving sideways interoperability between xrtpy, aiapy, emtoolkit, and other PyHC packages. In particular, the participants discussed ways to make a common object to represent temperature response functions across packages, and developed some prototypes. The participants of this hackathon were Joy Velasquez (XRTpy), Nick Murphy

¹² <https://gallery.ecr.aws/q3h7b4o8/helio-notebook-pyhc>

¹³ <https://github.com/sapols/pyhc-environment-files/tree/main>

(PlasmaPy), Jonathan Slavin (XRTpy), Joe Plowman (emtoolkit), and Will Barnes (SunPy and AIapy). In the end, progress was also made towards a common interface for creating temperature responses for instruments. Work needs to be continued, possibly funded.

General Meeting Notes

- Notable lack of AI/ML capabilities in the packages, possibly due to lack of PyHC advertisement in those communities.
- Community agreed to have a third category on the PyHC project page: (Unevaluated, Confirmed, and Core). Unanimous agreement to remove the Python 3 column and replace it with a 'Latest Update' column (or similar) as a measure of whether the package is still 'alive'.
- Classes on software basics (clean software practices and building a package) and tutorials (e.g. Pangeo in Heliophysics) were reasonably well-received. Should possibly be delegated to the summer school, though, to reach the intended audience.
- The unconference format was a great success! Attendees submitted and voted upon possible discussion topics before the dedicated sessions. After merging similar topics, the top few topics were chosen and discussed during the unconference sessions, and the remaining ones were delegated to upcoming telecons.
- AI technology is almost advanced enough to develop a PyHC chat bot to help visitors discover PyHC package capabilities and create code snippets. Shawn worries (unnecessarily) that AI will soon replace him, but someone still needs to keep the AI straight. Unanimous agreement that a beta version of the PyHC chat bot, when ready, should be made available to those interested (not the public).
- Shawn Polson presented on a TESS session he's spearheading to collaborate on a PyHC project to serve real-time data in a display at TESS. Kamodo (modeled data), iSWA (CCMC) and HAPI (APL) offered initial interest. It's possible other PyHC packages were hesitant to volunteer right away due to the funding issue mentioned earlier. Part of the motivation here is to get real-time capabilities into PyHC packages. If HAPI can get funding to serve real-time data, then many PyHC packages should be able to easily use that interface to incorporate real-time data into their visualization. For the session, it would be ideal to show some data sources that change with time during the eclipse and some that don't.
- The issue of long term code permanence came up. Two mentioned ways to achieve this is to ensure the code runs on many systems now so it can run on some systems later (e.g. pip install works on Linux, Mac and Windows - already a PyHC standard), move codes in licensed languages to free ones (e.g. IDL to Python), and to move towards code-free interfaces (e.g. GUIs). Unit tests are critical in the language transition process. SolarSoft and SPEDAS (both IDL packages) need support/funding to make this transition. Can AI

tools be used to speed up this process? GUI implementation can be made reproducible by allowing users to download a script encoding the user's selections.

- PyHC representation in the Frontiers of Astronomy and Space Sciences: Snakes on a Spaceship was good. Do something similar every few years? Next time, include a paper on technical advances in PyHC (e.g. summer school, the PyHC reference environment,, etc) and how PyHC is supporting the community's pursuit of open science (e.g. community involvement, software citation tracking, etc).

Improving PyHC (meetings and overall)

- In the future, consider modifying core package presentations to give a short description, an update, and to describe one or more current challenges for that package. Some already loosely used this format, but it would be ideal for all the core packages to do this. This approach is also expected to promote better discussions.
- Provide more discussion time after each core presentation is completed to brainstorm on the stated problem, and a net discussion time after all core presentations are completed to discuss broader issues (e.g. advancing our packages' interoperability, ideas for collaborations, overlaps in development goals, etc).
- A conversation coming up at DASH aims to make progress on interoperability between PyHC packages, particularly for coordinate conversions¹⁴. Would be good to pinpoint similar areas in PyHC packages where interoperability could be improved to encourage similar future sessions (e.g. unit conversions), and consider hosting those capabilities on the HDRL website (e.g. a coordinate conversion webpage). Although visualization is a tempting choice, the visualizations standard for each domain are unique enough to keep the capabilities separate in the packages. Providing for data interoperability between the packages could be one way to broaden the use of those visualization capabilities across packages (e.g. orbit plotting in pysat used for geospace data from SpacePy or modeled data interpolated into a satellite orbit from Kamodo).
- One idea to deepen PyHC's integration into infrastructure is to collaborate with infrastructure entities (e.g. SPDF, SDAC, interested academic institutions and laboratories, etc) to use PyHC packages to satisfy open science requirements for their data (e.g. data access through HAPI/fido, or a new option for higher quality quick-look plots through an embedded GUI developed by the package) instead of infrastructure entities (new and current) developing these capabilities independently. Incorporating the repositories' quick-look plotting capabilities into PyHC packages or as a separate PyHC package could also be a way to increase interoperability between data and software. Can Python versions of popular tools be created (e.g. pyAutoPlot) and included in PyHC?

¹⁴ <http://dash.heliophysics.net/sessions.html#6>

- Another way to deepen PyHC’s role in the community is to act on the suggestion to create an army of paid PyHC trainers (see the Open Science Session section). This team will act as PyHC representatives at various conferences and schools to teach the community how to use the various PyHC packages to perform analyses relevant to each domain. This could be funded by the current push for open science (NSF, NASA and others), by collaborating with other educational efforts (e.g. NASA’s HEAT¹⁵ and SCoPE¹⁶ programs, and or by a NASA ROSES or NSF funding call. Original and useful contributions to their tutorial materials should be compensated appropriately by PyHC using a new added section of their budget. These tutors need to have a dedicated (and paid) training session led by PyHC software developers and leadership staff to properly prepare them for these responsibilities. Successful completion of this training should result in a special ‘PyHC Trainer’ badge that should be worn at conferences (e.g. a polo with the logo and related text or a pin/hat/something). The training could be developed in collaboration with the Software Carpentries group. The funding structure could be modeled after the NASA TOPS Champions program.
- Encouraging PyHC packages to develop GUIs (code-free interfaces) could lead to a PyHC analysis website in collaboration with HelioCloud and HDRL. See VEDA¹⁷ for how this is being done in Earth Science. Developing this in Heliophysics with PyHC would be a great community resource and would deepen PyHC’s permanence in the Heliophysics Community. We could include preliminary work towards this in a 5-year vision, but additional funding for GUI/UI/UX and website development will be needed. One way to work towards this goal would be for honorarium to be made available to Heliophysics community members to contribute quality multi-package tutorials to the PyHC Gallery (subject to review by PyHC leadership and representatives from the software packages included in the tutorials). Those tutorials could then be used to design a website interface to accomplish the same analysis through a website hosted by HelioCloud (see below).
- It will be advantageous for infrastructure resources such as SPDF to collaborate with PyHC to advance our infrastructure capabilities for datasets by streamlining user access to the data through analysis packages. Such access could be added to the dataset entries on the search result pages by simply adding a link on that entry titled ‘Analyze with pySPEDAS’ or the appropriate package(s) for the dataset, which will lead to a webpage interface hosting various analysis capabilities powered by that package (e.g. VEDA linked above, but for Heliophysics). Until the GUI version of those analyses methods are developed, the link can instead either lead to a static notebook tutorial hosted on PyHC’s

¹⁵ <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/heat/home/>

¹⁶ <https://science.nasa.gov/science-activation-team/smd-community-of-practice-for-education>

¹⁷ <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/dashboard/>

website or an executable version of the same notebook on HelioCloud (with a possible limit on compute).

- More ideas on how to incorporate and support the community's pursuit of open science will be included in a future report, along with recommendations for various interested parties (e.g. NASA, commercial, mission groups, educators, etc) and a vision to move forward, including specific tasks to focus on in the next year, 5 years, and so on.

Next Steps

- The DASH/IHDEA meetings are in October of this year, with many PyHC members leading sessions.
- The spring meeting next year will be virtual only due to the PyHC summer school next year. Need to determine a good timeline for planning (both the logistics and the material).
- The fall PyHC meeting will be reduced to a gathering at the DASH meeting.
- Unconference topics not discussed will be telecon topics in the near future.
 - Python for Coders (Intro to Python tutorial for scientists just getting started in Python)
 - How should PyHC projects facilitate operation in a cloud environment? In particular, how do we reference data not directly in the local filesystem without having to write cloud access routines in every file reader?
 - What changes need to be made to run PyHC package on data living in S3 buckets
 - Docker images published yearly/bi-yearly with all PyHC packages installed
 - How to connect infrastructure to scientific discovery/impact
 - Create better understanding of governance of scientific infrastructure and how to democratize that process
 - Discuss how we can shift the PyHC's summer school focus off of 'how to use our packages' to 'How to analyze data from multiple missions (with our packages).'
 - Discussion of how to discover, capture, and promote best practices and standards that the community has agreed upon? Similar to the PEP process. (Short title: PyHC Enhancement Proposal process)
 - Request in lunch session: Want a tool like HelioViewer for other domains to see how data from different instruments fit together. How can PyHC address this issue?
 - Pros and cons of various approaches on community/contribution rules
 - Discussion of what the vision is for PyHC packages as a whole for the next five years
- PyHC has a scheduled poster session at the upcoming AGU 2023 meeting in San Francisco, CA, "SH012-I. Implementations in Python for Solar and Space Physics Poster". Wednesday, 13 December 2023, 14:10 - 18:30 local time.

- Several other relevant sessions are upcoming as well. See meeting agenda for more details¹⁸.

References

Dowler, P., D. Tody and F. Bonnarel (2016). IVOA Simple Image Access.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1601.00519> and <https://www.ivoa.net/documents/SIA/>

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2018). *Open Source Software Policy Options for NASA Earth and Space Sciences*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226%2F25217>

¹⁸ <https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm23/meetingapp.cgi/Home/0>

Final agenda

	Start Time (MDT)	End Time (MDT)	Duration (min)	Type	Title	Presenter/Discussion Lead
Tuesday, May 16						
Tue, May 16, 23	9:15	9:20	0:05	Presentation	Introductions, welcome, meeting goals	Julie Barnum
Tue, May 16, 23	9:20	9:40	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: HAPI</i>	Jon V.
Tue, May 16, 23	9:40	10:00	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: PlasmaPy</i>	Nick M.
Tue, May 16, 23	10:00	10:20	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: SunPy</i>	Will B.
Tue, May 16, 23	10:20	10:47	0:27		Break	
Tue, May 16, 23	10:47	11:07	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: SpacePy</i>	Jon N
Tue, May 16, 23	11:07	11:27	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: pysat</i>	Russell S
Tue, May 16, 23	11:27	11:47	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: Kamodo</i>	Darren D.Z.
Tue, May 16, 23	11:47	12:07	0:20	Presentation	<i>Overview and Updates of Core Packages: PySPEDAS</i>	Jim L.
Tue, May 16, 23	12:07	13:15	1:08		Lunch	
Tue, May 16, 23	13:15	13:35	0:20	Presentation	<i>Geomagnetic and high latitude coordinate tools</i>	Angeline Burrell
Tue, May 16, 23	13:35	13:55	0:20	Presentation	<i>XRTpy intro</i>	Joy Velasquez
Tue, May 16, 23	13:55	14:15	0:20	Presentation	CCSDSPy intro	Daniel E. da Silva
Tue, May 16, 23	14:15	14:35	0:20	Presentation	HITS update	Alec Engell
Tue, May 16, 23	14:35	14:50	0:15	Discussion	<i>Further subdividing PyHC Projects</i>	Shawn Polson/Julie Barnum
Tue, May 16, 23	14:50	15:00	0:10		Break	
Tue, May 16, 23	15:00	16:00	1:00	Discussion	<i>Geomagnetic Field Models within Heliophysics</i>	Ashley Smith (and others)
Tue, May 16, 23	16:00	17:30	1:30	Discussion	<i>PyHC Executable Paper: the science version</i>	Rebecca Ringuette

Wednesday, May 17						
Wed, May 17, 23	9:00	9:30	0:30	Tutorial	Geomagnetic datacubes	Ashley Smith
Wed, May 17, 23	9:30	10:15	0:45	Tutorial	HelioCloud (the basics and recent updates)	Brian Thomas et al.
Wed, May 17, 23	10:15	11:10	0:55	Tutorial	Package Submission to PyHC	Shawn Polson
Wed, May 17, 23	11:10	11:25	0:15		Break	
Wed, May 17, 23	11:25	11:55	0:30	Tutorial	Clean code refresher	Nick Murphy
Wed, May 17, 23	11:55	12:10	0:15	Discussion	Unconference voting/organizing	
Wed, May 17, 23	12:10	13:25	1:15		Lunch	
Wed, May 17, 23	13:25	14:40	1:15	Unconference	Unconference Sessions	
				Topic 1	Running on the cloud/cloud enabling	
Wed, May 17, 23	14:40	14:55	0:15		Break	
Wed, May 17, 23	14:40	15:55	1:15	Unconference	Unconference Sessions	
				Topic 2	Maintainer burnout	
				Topic 3	Proposal development?	
Wed, May 17, 23	15:55	16:10	0:15	Discussion	Unconference summaries	
Wed, May 17, 23	16:10	16:40	0:30	Discussion	Hackathon Planning	
Wed, May 17, 23	19:00				Group Dinner at Rio Grande on Walnut Street	
Thursday, May 18						
Thu, May 18, 23	9:10	9:40	0:30	Presentation/Discussion	"Heliophysics ScienceCore curriculum development with emphasis on knowledge representation techniques to increase usability of NASA cloud-based datasets" - An overview and where PyHC fits in	Donny Winston
Thu, May 18, 23	9:40	10:10	0:30	Presentation	pyOpenSci intro	Leah Wasser
Thu, May 18, 23	10:10	11:10	1:00	Presentation/Discussion	ChatGPT and PyHC	Shawn Polson

Thu, May 18, 23	11:10	11:55	0:45	Discussion	PyHC's TESS '24 Solar Eclipse Event	Shawn Polson
Thu, May 18, 23	11:55	12:10	0:15	Discussion	Wrap Up	Julie Barnum
			Optiona l Hackat hon Afterno on			
Thu, May 18, 23	12:00	17:00	5:00	Hackathon	Hackathon Session (Optional)	